

An Important Factor in Solving the Poor Problem

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ABSTRACT: This article highlights the role of farms in improving the welfare of the population, in particular, in Namangan region, the specifics of the solution of the problem of poverty through the development of farms in Namangan region.

KEYWORDS-Farms, poverty, entrepreneurship, cluster, pandemic, credit.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, the pandemic, which is leaving a complex mark on the world economy, is having a negative impact on all sectors of the economy, from large enterprises to small businesses and private entrepreneurship. In order to prevent such negative consequences, a new system of business support is being introduced in our country.

Due to the conditions created by our state, the number of people willing to engage in entrepreneurial activities is growing. Especially in rural areas, they are engaged in horticulture, horticulture, horticulture, beekeeping, animal husbandry, poultry, fisheries, handicrafts, services and other industries due to the nature of the region. It is obvious that special attention is paid to the development of family business, especially small farms. This is not only a socio-economic task, but also a political goal aimed at changing the worldview of our people, sharply increasing their interest in earning income through labor. Therefore, in recent years, the state has adopted a number of laws, resolutions and regulations on the effective use of public lands, some laws have been amended. A separate deputy position has been introduced in the mahalla, which deals with gardening.

The Council of Farmers, Dehkan Farms and Landowners of Uzbekistan and its territorial subdivisions have also been established. Separately, 224 enterprises "Tomorqa Xizmati" have been set up to supply seeds and seedlings and provide services. 350 billion soums have been allocated from the state budget for the implementation of new projects on the farm, and a fund has been set up under the Farmers' Council. Based on today's demand, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction was established. It is obvious that a new system has been introduced, which does not exist before, providing assistance to the population, supplying and financing material resources. As long as the state creates all conditions for the development of farms, it is safe to say that today the effective use of these opportunities has become a necessity and an obligation. This is because at a time when the whole world is threatened by the coronavirus pandemic, the development of horticulture is becoming a more serious issue. This issue was highlighted at a video conference chaired by President Sh. Mirziyoyev on April 8, 2020, dedicated to the analysis of the effectiveness of work in the fight against the coronavirus pandemic and the development of horticulture, an important source of food security, employment and income. The issues of supply of cultivated products to domestic and foreign markets were also considered.

II. THE MAIN PART

In Namangan region, as in all regions of the country, a program of promising measures for the development of horticulture has been created. There are 252.0 thousand hectares of irrigated land in the region, of which 31.9 thousand hectares are residential plots. Given today's requirements, the main focus is on the efficient use of farmland. This is because the majority of the province's population lives in rural areas and a certain stratum of them are poor families.

There are exemplary farms in a number of districts of the region, which are harvested 2-3 times a year from 8-10 acres of land and earn 50-60 million soums, and some families earn more than 100 million soums, which is an example for other families.

An Important Factor in Solving the Poor Problem

According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 30, 2020 No 53, khokims of Naryn, Uychi, Turakurgan, Namangan districts jointly on the basis of the principles of "Source of income", "One neighborhood one product", "From field to table" practical and demonstration seminars were organized.

Based on the above considerations, it can be said that given the complex situation caused by the coronavirus pandemic, sowing 2-3 times and getting additional yields in all farms is one of the priority tasks today. With this in mind, the construction of compact greenhouses in homes is also important.

Last year, 2,670 modern compact greenhouses were established in Namangan region. This work will continue in 2021, and it is planned to build a total of 4,400 light greenhouses in 300-500 houses in each district, and 527 of them have been built and put into operation.

During his visit to Namangan region in June 2020, President Mirziyoyev during his visit to Namangan region to get acquainted with major projects, to communicate with the population, to provide employment and a stable source of income for unemployed, low-income, poor families. Had given a number of assignments. On the basis of these tasks, the project "Greenhouse for a thousand families in one place" was implemented in the region in cooperation with the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations. In particular, Golden Nats Namangan Agro Network Service LLC has built 1,000 2-storey greenhouses on 36 hectares of land in Chartak district, which has not been used for many years. The project, worth 13 billion soums, received 6.7 billion soums in subsidies from the Employment Promotion Fund and 6.3 billion soums in soft loans from commercial banks.

According to the study, these greenhouses produce high-quality products that meet the requirements of foreign countries on the basis of the principle of "one neighborhood - one product." Another advantage is that seedlings, water, mineral fertilizers and market supply in the cultivation of the product are guaranteed by the leading entrepreneur. In greenhouses it is possible to grow crops up to 3 times a year. According to experts, 700 tomato seedlings were planted in one greenhouse. Each bush can yield 4-5 kg of seedlings. For example, if the average price of 1 kg of tomatoes (in the relevant months) is 3 thousand soums, the first harvest can earn 7-8 million soums.

As mentioned above, these greenhouses, built on the land of Baland Adir, which has not been used for many years, were given to low-income families on a soft loan for 3 years. Upon repayment of the loan, the 2-storey greenhouse will be fully registered in the name of citizens. Such material interest encourages people to use greenhouse equipment, irrigation systems and land efficiently. That is, it radically changes people's attitudes toward property, labor, and the products they grow. This is the implementation of the program of measures to reduce poverty in our country and the practical result of socio-economic reforms.

The new tactic of the new Uzbekistan, that is, a new economic measure, is to develop the land, to give it to entrepreneurs who want to work by extracting water from vertical wells. Our land is a paradise, we need to use it to set an example for other regions and awaken people. We give the husband, the seedling, the seed, the money, provided that it is used year after year, the rest of the effort should be from the people themselves. If we do not, we will not have results tomorrow (3). In accordance with the relevant resolutions and decrees of the President, 5,361 hectares of land were developed in Namangan region in 2020 and 1,496 hectares of new gardens were established.

"Poverty reduction is the awakening of entrepreneurial spirit in the population, the full realization of human potential and strength, the implementation of a comprehensive socio-economic policy to create new jobs ... Entrepreneurship, initiative, especially youth and women to solve social problems on the ground It is necessary to give priority to the support of entrepreneurship," said President Mirziyoyev in his speech at a meeting with activists of Namangan region in June 2020. (4)

Today's experience shows that it is necessary to provide employment and lift people out of poverty through regular income. Because more than 24,300 poor families and 57,000 more unemployed are registered in the region. With this in mind, a program of measures for 2020-2022 to ensure employment through the organization of various forms of entrepreneurship in the districts has been developed. In this regard, the work carried out in Chartak, Turakurgan, Uchkurgan and Uychi districts can be cited as an example. In particular, at the beginning of 2020, 1920 poor families were registered in Uychi district, and measures were taken to provide them with employment and permanent income on this basis. To date, the deputies of the District Council have studied each family and issued the relevant acts, and 1052 families were removed from the list of poor families by the decision of the session. As a result, 868 families remained on the list of poor families.

Of these poor families, 79 were given cattle, 212 were sheep, 108 were poultry, 2 were bees, and 13 were rented land. Greenhouses were built for 86 families. In addition, 169 people were provided with permanent jobs, 2 with medicines and 47 with cash. It is obvious that the district provides practical assistance to every citizen in the implementation of the tasks set out in the poverty alleviation program.

An Important Factor in Solving the Poor Problem

Also, under the program "Every family is an entrepreneur" Agrobank and People's Bank of the district allocated a total of 895 citizens (including 46 legal entities) 18 billion 149 million soums for the purchase of livestock, fisheries, greenhouses, horticulture and equipment.

From the above data, it is clear that the conditions are being created for people to work, earn money through entrepreneurship. However, the created opportunities are not being used effectively in all regions of the region. In particular, in Turakurgan, Kosonsoy, Uchkurgan, Chartak, Yangikurgan districts it was found that there is a lack of greenhouses in households and fruit trees and vines are not planted in the gardens. In the words of President Sh. Mirziyoyev, this situation should be considered a betrayal of the country and the land in the current test period, not to plant crops, to leave them unattended. Because the coronavirus pandemic has clearly shown that policies and measures on food security in countries around the world are insufficient.

Therefore, the heads of regional, district khokimiyats, farms councils, the Ministry of Labor, mahalla committees and public receptions, heads of 4 sectors should visit each house in the region to study the establishment of greenhouses for planting various crops, fruit trees and vines and solve existing problems. Should provide practical assistance.

As the President Sh. Mirziyoyev said in his address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan: Assessment of the real situation in the regions on poverty reduction, control over the implementation of the work should be the focus of the Oliy Majlis chambers and local councils.

In general, each district and city mayor must develop a targeted poverty reduction program in their area within a month and report quarterly to the public on its implementation in local councils and through the media. This issue should become the primary task of all leaders and a key criterion for evaluating performance.

It should be noted that some people think that the assistance provided by the state and the favorable conditions created are permanent. Instead of trying to meet the needs of their families and the local market by borrowing money, raising livestock, and buying a variety of livestock products, this category of people sells their livestock on credit. They use the money to meet their other needs. There are also cases when the given seeds, seedlings of fruit trees are not planted in time, and the planted ones are not cared for enough. Such negative situations lead to untimely repayment of loans issued by banks. Even some families do not even think about repaying the loan at all. It is as if the loan was given to them as "Exson". In fact, a loan is an obligation, a responsibility. It means getting out of poverty by employing family members and earning income on that basis. It is time to radically change the worldview of such fuzzy, dependent people.

As the President Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, "the most important factor in overcoming poverty should be human aspirations, based on their own strength, the movement towards a clear goal." (4)

In the approaching spring months, it is advisable to pay more attention to the care of vegetable crops grown in greenhouses, cultivating the land and planting a variety of crops and fruit seedlings. In this way, the regions will be able to fully meet the demand for food products, increase the income of the population and, on this basis, increase their welfare.

In our opinion, in order to further develop horticulture, which is one of the important factors in solving future socio-economic problems, and on this basis to get out of poverty, it is expedient to pay attention to the following.

First, to ensure the unconditional implementation of laws, forms and decisions issued by the state on the development of farms. Appointment of officials to monitor their implementation and regular analysis of their reports, as well as the identification of appropriate measures.

Second, to systematically study the use of farmland at the crossroads of community gatherings. Regular media coverage of the experiences of exemplary landowners.

Third, to ensure the sustainability of the links between the supply of seeds, seedlings, chemicals, mineral fertilizers to livestock, fodder for livestock, veterinary services.

Fourth, to conclude preliminary contracts with enterprises purchasing, storing and processing agricultural products grown on the farms and to ensure their timely and strict implementation, ie to organize the cultivation of crops in a cluster manner.

Fifth, the targeted and timely use of bank loans, livestock, seeds and seedlings by families engaged in horticulture should be regularly monitored by officials and measures should be taken to eliminate the identified shortcomings.

Sixth, to conduct advocacy and advocacy work at bank meetings and community gatherings to explain the effective use and timely repayment of loans provided by gardeners.

Seventh, to ensure timely repayment of loans provided by banks to families, to impose economic sanctions on citizens who do not use credit resources in a targeted manner and do not repay them on time.

An Important Factor in Solving the Poor Problem

Eighth, the introduction of a new mechanism based on the principle of "Finance, Skills" to lift every citizen included in the "Iron Book" from poverty in order to take advantage of various benefits.

Ninth, to organize a practical and demonstration seminar on the basis of the principles of "Source of income in the field", "One neighborhood - one product", "From the field to the table" in the regions. Regular media coverage of the activities of exemplary farms and the accumulated experience.

CONCLUSIONS

In short, today, farms play an important role in solving the problem of poverty through employment and regular income. With this in mind, the necessary conditions are being created for the sustainable development of farms. The purpose of these is to positively address the socio-economic problems of our country.

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